

BREAST CANCER DEVELOPMENT

By Edwin Amuga

Abstract

Breast malignancy is a burdensome illness in the lives of women and communities globally. One in eight women in the world today stands a risk of developing breast cancer as compared to men who are at one in a thousand breast cancer risks. Most breast cancer cases are linked to breast somatic cells mutations acquirable during one's lifetime. In the hereditary scenario, there are specific genetic factors that are involved and determine the inherited breast cancer risk and are attributed to inherited BRCA2 BRCA1 genes mutations whereas breast malignancy risk that's not inherited have been linked to mutations in the ATM, STK11, CDH1, PTEN, TP53, PALB2 and CHEK2 and have been established to confer the risk of developing malignancy. Understanding the functional significance of hereditary mutations is important in informing the prevention of breast cancer and inform treatment strategies and this paper intends to inform this understanding.

Introduction

Breast cancer is one of the most common types of cancer in women that also affects men albeit on rare occasions. Cancer types can be categorized into three distinct types. The Ductal carcinoma in situ abbreviated as DCIS occurs in the epithelial cells that line the breast ducts. A significant number of studies reveals that this type of cancer is 30% likely to be invasive if not

treated. Another breast cancer type Lobular carcinoma in situ, LCIS is developed in the milk-producing glands and has an increased risk for invasive cancer. Most breast cancer cases advance to be either invasive or infiltrating, and the intervention type depends on the disease developmental stage (Tung, Battelli, Allen, Kaldate, Bhatnagar, Bowels & Krejdovsky, 2015). Breast cancer is increasingly being considered a group of diseases that are differentiated by their respective molecular subtypes including clinical behaviors, risk factors, and treatment responses. Such biological markers as estrogen receptor status, progesterone receptor status and human epidermal growth factor receptor are used to classify breast cancer into treatment classes. This transcriptional tumor profiling leads to the second system of classification, which is though related to biomarkers, utilizing 50 genes expression level PAM50 score used to standardize subtype classification. PAM50 is used as cancer progression and patient survival predictive tool.

BRCA1 and BRCA2 are two very different genes that suppress tumor and are essential in responding to cellular stress through DNA repair process activation. Germline mutation of these genes renders individuals susceptible to develop types of cancer including ovarian, pancreatic, and prostate and breast cancer. Observations indicate that BRCA genes could function in specific tissues such as in breasts and the ovary. Functional studies have revealed that these genes control chromatin cell cycle, transcription remodeling, and DNA repair process in many different organs as they have interactions with a significant number of proteins involved in the repair of DNA and take part in Fanconi anemia, a condition attributed to DNA repair proteins defects with such symptoms as instability in the genomes and increased risk of developing cancer. The regulatory roles of these genes in controlling cell cycle checkpoints and DNA repair mechanisms are linked to tumor suppressing activities. Germline mutation of BRCA 1 and 2 genes is associated with breast and ovarian cancer development.

BRCA1 gene

BRCA1 was cloned and located in the human chromosome n 1994. Several studies have investigated the functional role of the gene with its full length established to be encoded by 24 exons. The gene has been revealed to be a multi-functional protein that interacts with diverse protein partners in a range of cell compartments thereby playing essential parts in a variety of cellular passageways including genetic instability, apoptosis, arresting cell cycles, activation of transcription, repair of damages in the DNA and cancer development. BRCA1 gene mutation has been connected to increased ovarian and breast cancer risk over a lifetime. Most risk factors and risk modifiers of tumorigenesis operate in a similar manner in BRCA mutation carriers (Finch, Lubinski, Moller, Singer, Karlan, Senter & Huzarski, 2014).

BRCA mutation in cancer patients has been perceived in three domains. These are the N-terminal RING domain that is programmed by 2 to 7 exons (amino acids 1-109), exon coding regions 11 to 13 and BRCA1 C-terminus that is prearranged by 16 to 24 exons with 1650 to 1863 amino acids or the BCRT domain. These domains are crucial in interactions with partner proteins and BRCA1 subcellular localization.

The BRCA1 RING domain is made up of a RIND finger motif that corresponds to 24 to 64 residues and is a highly conserved domain playing the crucial part in ubiquitination passageways and interrelates with RING domain that contains protein BARD1, a protein related with BRCA1. Studies on yeast reveal that BARD1 and BRCA1 RING finger motifs are necessary for the interaction and identify discrete nuclear foci on damaged replicating DNA structures in the cell cycle progression S-phase by the heteromeric complex. This domain sees to an E3 ubiquitination activity of ligase of BRCA1 dramatically increasing the formation of the

BARD1-BRCA1 heterodimer that knocks out mice in embryonic lethality and mutation in BARD1 which are prevalent in hereditary ovarian and breast cancers.

Also crucial in BRCA1 tumor suppression are Exons 11- 13 as they contain large clinically relevant mutation percentages. This is a middle region of BRCA1 that interacts with some proteins take part such cellular pathways as transcription, the repair of the DNA, and progression of the cell cycle and communicating with such partners as RAD51, RAD50, c-Myc, and retinoblastoma protein (Rb). Exon 11 has two NLSs that serve to encode around 60% BRCA1 protein. The location of the sequences are in between 501 and 507 and 607 and 614 amino acids to facilitate the interaction with importin-alpha thereby mediating the conveyance of BRCA1 to the nucleus from the cytosol. Mutations in the sequence result in a shift towards the BRCA1 cytosol localization and increased mutations that are not repaired and malignancies due to abnormalities in the chromosome

The C-terminal BCRT domain is located among 1650 and 1863 amino acids that interact with substrates kinases ATR and ATM that activate DNA damage. This area also interacts with a range of regulators of transcriptions including p53 and BACH1 and proteins responsible for the repair of DNA such as CtIP and CCDC98. mutations in this domain especially in the hydrophobic residues result in the inability to interact with phosphoproteins as observed in ovarian and breast cancers indicating that BRCA1 C-terminus is involved in the suppression of tumor (Finch, Lubinski, Moller, Singer, Karlan, Senter & Huzarski, 2014). The domain has also been reported to mediate binding activity in DNA and interaction with other proteins.

BRCA 1 was initially known as a nuclear phosphoprotein in normal cells and tumor cells that line tissues and not in breast and ovary. BRCA1 has been observed to be predominantly

located in the cytoplasm. Other studies claim that the gene is located in the nuclei of both normal and cancer cells. Some studies have also indicated that the gene secretes 190kDa tumor-suppressing proteins and not the widely known 220-230 kDa proteins. These opposing observations indicate that BRCA1 has a functionally different alternative interwoven transcription. The alternative merging of the BRCA1 gene is common and relates to its tumorigenesis function. A great number of BRCA1 merger variants have been located in different types of tissues and cells through the functional significance of most of the still remains unknown. There are possibly two transcripts of exon 1 of BRCA1, that is, exon 1a and exon 1b, with exon 1a found in the milk-producing glands and transcripts with 1b situated in the placenta/. This indicates that BRCA1 transcript variants are distributed in specific tissues. Recent studies indicate that BRCA1 expressions of spliced variants are linked with repair of radiation-induced DNA double-strand break in NCF-7 breast cancer cells.

BRCA1 functional diversity

BRCA1 serves to regulate a range of cellular function in different compartments of the cells. Phosphorylated BRCA1 in the S-phase of the cell cycle or genotoxic stress translocate to the nucleus to regulate the repair process of damaged DNA, the replication of the DNA, transactivation of the gene, inactivation of the X chromosome. BRCA1 protein level analysis reveals that its expression remains low at G0 and G1 phases but is increased from G1 in the S-phase checkpoint and is maintained throughout the S-phase, the G2 and the M phase. During the S-phase, BRCA1 undergoes hyperphosphorylation and after the M-phase undergoes dephosphorylation (Coates, Winer, Goldhirsch, Gleber, Gnant, Piccart-Gebhart & Baselga, 2015). Damage of the DNA effects BRCA1 nuclear translocation and it becomes phosphorylated through activated kinases of DNA damage such as the ATR, ATM, AND Chk1 or Chk2 with the

presence of two exons 11 NLS that effect the nuclear translocation of BRCA1. BARD1 as binding partner serves as an alternative pathway of BRCA1 via RING domain interaction suggesting a mechanism for nuclear localization of alternatively merged BRCA1 variants interwoven with exon II. BRCA1 N-terminus mechanistically has two sequences for nuclear export thereby facilitating the protein1 to maintain the chromosome region (CRM1) thereby mediating BRCA1 export from the nucleus. BRCA1 Nuclear export sequence is directly masked by BARD1 that utilizes its own Nuclear Localization Sequence ensuring efficient BRCA1. BRCA1 binding protein 2 (BRAP 2) binds the nuclear localization sequence of BRCA1 facilitating the retention of the cytoplasm as it disrupts importin-alpha interaction which is a nuclear import receptor.

The functions of BRCA1 in the cytoplasm include regulating mitotic cell division, rearranging cytoskeleton, apoptosis, and repair of mitochondrion genome. The BRCA1/BARD1 E3 ubiquitin ligase activity regulates duplication in the centrosome and spindle pole assembly during mitosis. BRCA1 also is involved in the mitotic checkpoint, NES mutation, leptomycin B cell treatment. Leptomycin B is a CRM export inhibitor that caused BRCA1 transportation reduction into the centromere and in the process also reduces the overall exchange and retention rate. BRCA1 also ubiquitinates other centromere proteins such as the nucleophosmin, a protein that plays a crucial role in centrosome duplication. Bsc-2 and AKT1 can also redirect BRCA1 to the mitochondrion and endoplasmic reticulum.

BRCA1's best-known functioning in the DNA repair pathway is suppressing mutation and repair of the damaged DNA double-strand break. The gene has also been associated with cellular growth and proliferation and knockdown of growth of malignant and normal growth in the mammary cells especially in the breast and ovarian cancer cells. This role of the gene is

attributed to the Rb protein which is known to suppress tumor thereby controlling growth as it regulates cell cycle progression.

The gene plays a crucial role in regulating transcription since it interacts with many transcription factors such as the p53, c-Myc, CtIP, RNA polymerase II, Stat1 and ZBRK1. BRCA1 plays part in the core transcriptional machinery as it disrupts cancer-related mutations interaction with RNA polymerase. Some investigations have established that the gene autoregulates its transcription thereby maintaining the integrity of genome when responding to genotoxic stress (Tung, Battelli, Allen, Kaldate, Bhatnagar, Bowels & Krejdovsky, 2015). The gene interacts with retinoblastoma suppressor protein, RbAp46, in remodeling and modifying histone component complex. The gene also takes part in the reconstruction of the chromatin complex as it is a component of human SWI/SNF chromatin. The interaction of the gene with a range of different transcription factors happen within the regions between N and C terminus. The N-terminal amino acids sequences 240-800 are the regions where transcription factors STAT1 and p53 interact with the gene whereas the C-terminus amino acids sequences 1602-1863 form the regions where the gene interacts with CtIP.

It is therefore clear that besides the tumor suppression overall role of the gene, it also works as transcription co-activator or co-repressor adding to its overall role. There is little that is however known about target genes except for the BRCA1 gene itself, ANG1 and MAD2.

The BRCA2 gene

The gene was discovered in 1994 by Wooster and contains 27 exons with eight BRC motifs, which are internally repeated sequences that interact with RAD51. The exons structures of the BRCA1 and BRCA2 are similar with differences in homology of the sequence. The human

BRCA2 nuclear localization signals colocalize with BRCA1 in subnuclear foci in the somatic cells. The gene is also a crucial transcriptional co-regulator and interacts with SMAD3 in forming a complex that co-activates transcriptions that are dependent on Smad3 to activate PAI-1-plasminogen activator inhibitor-1 and works in conjunction with histone acetyltransferases in a transcription mediated by the androgen receptor.

Inherited are caused by BRCA1 and BRCA2 genes mutation with the loss of BRCA1 expression is responsible for 30-40% of sporadic malignancies. The lifetime breast malignancy risk posed by BRCA1 and BRCA2 mutation carriers stands at 40-80% whereas the breast malignancy development risk attributed to these two gene mutations in a lifetime is 45-60%. These mutation carriers are associated with risk for other malignancies including prostate, pancreatic, melanoma, endometrial, fallopian tube and colorectal cancers. Most patients diagnosed with breast cancer before menopause have BRCA1 mutation carriers with a high likelihood of 80% in comparison with non-hereditary breast cancer patients. Women that have BRCA mutation carriers have a 10-15% ovarian and breast cancer development risk in every ten years after menopause. Ovarian cancer development at younger ages is more likely to happen if one has BRCA1 mutation carriers than those with BRCA2 mutation carriers and sporadic cancer cases.

BRCA1 mutations observed in breast cancer are basal-like subtypes with over 70% mutated breast cancers expressing basal cytokeratins and do not express estrogen receptor. Breast tumors associated with BRCA2 have ER and lack p53 as compared to BRCA1 tumors breast tumors that are lack ER, progesterone receptor and epidermal growth factor but have p53. Sporadic breast cancer cases are more likely to have basal-like phenotype when they express the

loss of BRCA1. Consequently, tumors that have BRCA1 they luminal type and are linked to indolent clinical courses, endocrine therapy responsiveness, and improved survival.

Generally, the development of the basal-like phenotype is attributed to BRCA1 expression loss or function. The understanding of dysfunctional BRCA1 informs generation and pathogenesis of basal-like breast cancers and understanding of molecular events which cause basal-like malignancies.

BRCA deficient cancer therapies

There is no strategy for managing or reducing risks that are attributed to BRCA mutation carriers. Surveillance, risk-reducing surgery, and chemoprevention decision-making processes are very complex and are dependent on age, the history of the family on female breast cancer. This makes the management of cancers attributed to BRCA1 very complex and challenging meaning that there are no basic standards recommended for testing BRCA1 and BRCA2 mutations. In addition, there is no effective screening strategy since the available strategies, mammography and breast magnetic imaging, though helpful are insufficient and ineffective. Available treatment options include bilateral mastectomy and salpingo-oophorectomy and are dependent on the risk-reducing surgeries.

Surgical procedures aimed at reducing risk serve to protect against BRCA mutation carriers but are not recommended and preferred as targeted therapies for hereditary breast cancer management (Coates, Winer, Goldhirsch, Gleber, Gnant, Piccart-Gebhart & Baselga, 2015). The defects in the DNA that are attributed to the development of tumors provide an exploitable therapeutic strategy to managing cancerous cells. Tumor cells that are deficient of BRCA1 are vulnerable to DNA damaging agents including platinum-based chemotherapeutics such as

Cisplatin and Carboplatin as its derivation since the deficiency of the gene results in deregulation of DNA pathways (Kuchenbaecker, Hopper, Barnes, Phillips, Mooji, Roos-Blom & Goldgar, 2017). Another therapeutic treatment these cancer types is the use of enzyme polymerase (PARP) which repairs excision and takes part in single-strand DNA break repair. It can also be utilized in the therapeutic treatment of prostate, pancreatic, breast, and ovarian and even sporadic basal-like breast cancers.

Emerging challenges to breast cancer

DNA repair mechanism loss promotes genetic instability leading to the development of tumors. DNA repair mechanism that is defective also make DNA hypersensitive and damage chemotherapeutic agents such as Cisplatin and Carboplatin and PARP inhibitors that help manage these types of cancer that are attributed to BRCA2 and BRCA1 mutation carriers. In this response, other studies endorse that multiple mechanisms including altered drug transporters expression, microhomology-mediated end joints, and cellular oxidate state and translesion synthesis lead to unexpected resistance to drugs. Novel strategies reduce, prevent and overcome resistance to drugs in the secondary stage of BRCA1 and BRCA2 mutated ovarian and breast malignancy offering new challenges to the treatment of these types of cancer and success in managing this will increase patient survival.

References

- Coates, A. S., Winer, E. P., Goldhirsch, A., Gelber, R. D., Gnant, M., Piccart-Gebhart, M., ... & Baselga, J. (2015). Tailoring therapies—improving the management of early breast cancer: St Gallen International Expert Consensus on the Primary Therapy of Early Breast Cancer 2015. *Annals of oncology*, *26*(8), 1533-1546.
- Finch, A. P., Lubinski, J., Møller, P., Singer, C. F., Karlan, B., Senter, L., ... & Huzarski, T. (2014). Impact of oophorectomy on cancer incidence and mortality in women with a BRCA1 or BRCA2 mutation. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, *32*(15), 1547.
- Kuchenbaecker, K. B., Hopper, J. L., Barnes, D. R., Phillips, K. A., Mooij, T. M., Roos-Blom, M. J., ... & Goldgar, D. E. (2017). Risks of breast, ovarian, and contralateral breast cancer for BRCA1 and BRCA2 mutation carriers. *Jama*, *317*(23), 2402-2416.
- Tung, N., Battelli, C., Allen, B., Kaldate, R., Bhatnagar, S., Bowles, K., ... & Krejdovsky, J. (2015). Frequency of mutations in individuals with breast cancer referred for BRCA 1 and BRCA 2 testing using next-generation sequencing with a 25-gene panel. *Cancer*, *121*(1), 25-33.